

THE DEPENDENCE OF SUBSTRATE ENVIRONMENT AND IRRIGATION IN THE GROWING OF STRAWBERRY BY THE HYDROPONICS METHOD IN GREENHOUSE CONDITIONS

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Citation: Obidjon Kholdarovich Sindarov, Octavio Calvo-Gomez,

The Dependence of Substrate Environment and Irrigation in The Growing of Strawberry by The Hydroponics Method in Greenhouse Conditions. **Journal of Hydraulics and Environmental Engineering (JHEE)** 2025, 1(1).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16962368>

Academic Editors: L.Samiev

Received: 10.01.2025

Revised: 25.02.2025

Accepted: 13.03.2025

Published: 5.04.2025

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Abstract. This study examined the practical and economic impact of care strategies for growing strawberries in a greenhouse involving the use of polyethylene (PE) and polyolefin (PO) films with different light transmission properties. Six genetically different varieties were included in the study, including “Seolhyang,” “Maehyang,” “Jukhyang,” “Keumsil,” “King’s Berry,” and the Japanese “Yotsuboshi F1” hybrid. Studied parameters for the research included changes in stem growth, leaf development, yield indicators, and the organoleptic (taste and aroma) properties of the strawberries. During cultivation, the daytime and nighttime temperatures under the PE film averaged 22.5 °C and 15.4 °C, respectively, while under the PO film they averaged 23.6 °C during the day and 17.3 °C at night. Scientific analyses had revealed that insufficient light availability caused reduced productivity, lower SPAD index values, and a decreased leaf area, as it occurred under the PE film. On the other hand, the PO film yielded an additional 3.3–5.0 t/ha, confirming its superior light retention. Consequently, the PO film supported optimal photosynthetic activity, resulting in enhanced plant growth and higher overall yields.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda turli yorug‘lik uzatuvchanlik xususiyatlariga ega polietilen (PE) va poliolenfin (PO) plyonkalaridan foydalanish orqali issiqxonada qulupnay yetishtirish bo‘yicha amaliy hamda iqtisodiy ta‘sirga o‘rganildi. Tadqiqotga bachkildardan va urug‘dan o‘stirilgan genetik jihatdan har xil oltita nav kiritildi: “Seolhyang”, “Maehyang”, “Jukhyang”, “Keumsil”, “King’s Berry” va yapon “Yotsuboshi F1” gibridi. O‘rganilgan ko‘rsatkichlar poya o‘shishi, barglarning rivojlanishi, hosil miqdori va qulupnayning organoleptik (ta‘m va hid) xususiyatlarini o‘z ichiga oldi. Parvarish jarayonida PE plyonkasi ostida kunduzi o‘rtacha harorat 22,5 °C, kechasi esa 15,4 °C bo‘lgan bo‘lsa, PO plyonkasi ostida kunduzi 23,6 °C va kechasi 17,3 °C kuzatildi. Ilmiy tahlillar shuni ko‘rsatdiki, yorug‘lik yetishmasligi (ayniqsa PE plyonkasi ostida) hosildorlikning kamayishi, SPAD indeksining pasayishi va barg maydonining qisqarishiga sabab bo‘lgan. Boshqa tomondan, PO plyonkasi qo‘shimcha 3,3–5,0 t/ga hosil berib, o‘zining ustun yorug‘likni saqlash xususiyatini tasdiqladi. Natijada, PO plyonkasi optimal fotosintetik faoliyatni qo‘llab-quvvatlab, o‘simliklarning o‘shishi va umumiy hosildorlikni oshirdi.

Keywords: strawberry, film, harvest, temperature, pH, PE, PO.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the issue of food safety has become more and more urgent all over the world. Population growth is causing an increase in the demand for food products. Different regions of the world are experiencing severe droughts, storms and floods as a result of global warming [1].

The success of agricultural production may change in the short and long term, depending on the complex ecological effects of global warming and climate change [2]. Extremes of heat, cold, humidity and dryness negatively affect plants [3], [4], [5]. Several other factors, including trade conflicts, epidemics, plant diseases, rising prices in seeds and fertilizers, increased wages, floods, heat waves, and other weather changes may negatively impact agriculture. Furthermore, soil degradation, aquifer depletion, saltwater intrusion, runoff and eutrophication, and emissions (e.g., CO₂, H₂O, etc.) from modern intensive agriculture contribute to global warming and resource scarcity [6].

However, it is important to provide the population with fresh fruits and vegetables throughout the year. Over the years, international agriculture has gone through three main stages: primitive farming, traditional agriculture, and modern agriculture. During primitive farming, people worked with tools made of stone. In the stage of traditional agriculture, tools made of iron and wood were produced. Modern agriculture is characterized by the wide use of advanced technologies and agricultural machinery, which has elevated the agricultural economy to a new level [7].

Considering the morpho-biological characteristics of fresh fruits, there may be natural challenges in their cultivation that would restrict the ability to grow these crops in open fields. Consequently, protected environments, such as greenhouses, are commonly utilized to ensure a continuous supply of food products. It is important to maintain stable climatic conditions in greenhouses, and this process is often carried out by using gas and other fuel resources. As a result, this is one of the factors that increase economic costs for farmers in the process of growing products. In addition, the winter season is not always consistent, thus external temperature and humidity changes require additional adaptation measures of greenhouse conditions. Therefore, it is important to develop modern greenhouse technologies and increase energy efficiency.

In the case of South Korea as a reference model, regarding energy use in its greenhouses, approximately 71.0% of the total greenhouse area is unheated, since those structures are primarily low-tech plastic designs that only support vegetables growth in late winter and early spring. The largest source of energy for heated greenhouses in South Korea is oil, with diesel being the most popular fuel; however, its use has nearly halved over the past five years. In contrast, kerosene consumption has tripled during the same period. Additionally, gas, electricity and geothermal energy also have a growing trend. Recently built high-tech greenhouses tend to favour electricity as the energy source due to its affordability and convenience. Unlike the Netherlands, rural gas pipelines are rare in South Korea, prompting the South Korean government to promote geothermal energy through a subsidy program in 2010.

Several insights in agricultural production systems, value chains, and broader food systems have emerged with digitalization; these include smart agriculture, precision agriculture, decision agriculture, digital agriculture, and agriculture Numérique (in French, “numeric agriculture”) [8], [9]. With the development of information technology, modern agriculture is undergoing a digitization process. Digital agriculture is a data-driven management system that includes data collection, transmission, processing, digital control techniques, networking, and automation [10], [11].

Controlling greenhouses presents unique challenges because it requires systems capable of adapting to microclimate factors and ever-changing environmental conditions. In northern latitudes and harsh climates, heating and cooling costs for greenhouses can account for 70–85% of total operating expenses [12]. This is particularly concerning because farmers often lack adequate measurement, modelling, and dynamic control mechanisms to optimize inputs for plant

growth [13]. Additionally, farm-to-fork losses in the form of food waste can reach up to 40% due to extended supply chains [6].

In this context, we used modern techniques involving digitalization in agricultural system plus technological enhancements for improving cultivation of strawberry fruits in hydroponic conditions. Our experiment focused on the effects of Polyethylene (PE) and Polyolefin (PO) films with different light transmission capabilities on hydroponically grown strawberry varieties, specifically analysing their impact on plant growth, development, and fruit quality.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

- The experiment was conducted using strawberry (*Fragaria × ananassa* Duch.) varieties "Seolhyang", "Maehyang", "Jukhyang", "Kingberry", "Keumsil" and the Japanese hybrid "Yotsuboshi F1". Strawberry seedlings were selected in forms with 3-4 leaves and a crown diameter of 5-6 mm. Japanese hybrids grown from seed and studied in this work were also selected after reaching these parameters.

- Plants were placed in 60 × 34 × 10 cm propagation trays (Hwaseong Industrial Co. Ltd., Okcheon, Korea) during 2016–2021. Each pot was filled with a food substrate (coir) made of coconut husk. A mixture of CO (coir; Cocopeat Co. Ltd., Dummalasuriya, Sri Lanka) and MIX (coir: perlite = 8:2) was used as root medium.

- The nutrient solution was supplied to the strawberry plants through a drip irrigation system developed by the Gyeongsangnam-do Agricultural Research and Council. Composition of macro elements (in mg/L): NO_3^- -13.0, NH_4^+ -1.0, H_2PO_4^- -4.0, K^+ -6.0, Ca^{2+} -2, SO_4^{2-} -4.0; trace elements: Fe -3.0, B -0.5, Mn -0.5, Zn -0.2, Cu -0.04, Mo -0.04. Water analyses were as follows (in mg/L): Ca^{2+} -0.90, Mg^{2+} -0.49, SO_4^{2-} -0.31, and HCO_3^- -0.60, whereas K^+ , NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and H_2PO_4^- ions were not detected. In the first week, to activate young roots, the nutrient solution with parameters of electrical conductivity (EC) 0.3 dS m^{-1} and pH 5.8, was given 4 times a day (200 ml per plant).

- EC and pH levels were monitored using a pH/EC meter (HI-98130, Hanna Instruments Co. Ltd., USA). The average temperature and relative humidity were recorded on a data logger (TR-74Ui, T&D Co. Ltd., Japan) and were maintained at approximately 17 ± 5 °C and $42 \pm 5\%$, respectively.

- Physical (total porosity, cocopeat capacity, air void and bulk density) and chemical (EC and pH) properties of the substrate under the experimental conditions were measured according to the methods of Kim and Jeong (2003). EC and pH values were measured by Kim et al. (2016) using Enzo 8200M (GOnDO Electronic Co. Ltd., Taiwan).

- Since the light transmittance of a greenhouse film can affect plant photosynthesis, it was measured using a VTSYIQI Haze Meter Light Transmission Tester at the beginning and end of each year for both PE and PO coatings. The level of light transmission of PE and PO films was determined at the beginning of the 2016 season and at the end of the 2019 season. During the growing season, the amount of light was measured using an LI-1400 Light Meter (LI-COR Inc., USA), and the level of illumination was recorded.

- The planting dates of the studied varieties in the field experiments were as follows: in the 2016-2017 season, they were planted on October 1, in the 2017-2018 season, on October 5; and in the 2018-2019 season, on October 2. During the planting process, all seedlings were completely planted in one day.

- To compare strawberry plants growth under different conditions, we measured the following parameters: leaf band (petiole) length, leaf length, leaf width, number of leaves, Soil Plant Analysis Development (SPAD) values, crown diameter, root length, leaf area, and dry weight of new shoots

and roots. All measurements were taken at 14 and 28 days after cutting. Chlorophyll content was measured using a portable chlorophyll meter (SPAD-502, Konica Minolta Inc., Tokyo, Japan) and expressed as SPAD values. Fruit (crown or false fruit) diameters were measured using an electronic digital calliper (Vernier Calliper CD-20PX, Mitutoyo Co. Ltd., Kawasaki, Japan).

- A portable meter (FluorPen FP100, Photon Systems Instruments spol., Drasov, Czech Republic) was used to determine chlorophyll fluorescence. The fresh weight of shoots and roots was determined using an electronic scale (EW220-3NM, Kern & Sohn GmbH., Balingen, Germany), while the dry weight was determined by dried in an oven at 70 °C for 72 h and then weighing in an electronic ("Labntools" scales, Korea) scale. Leaf area was measured using a special leaf area meter (LI-3000, LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA).

- Data on the yield indicators of strawberry varieties and morpho-phenological observations were recorded on the first day of every month and analysed. For the varieties and hybrids included in the analysis, 25 plants were selected from each variant for phenological observation, and data was collected from these plants. Productivity was determined by weighing the yield.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Study of the effect of light transmission in relation to the film types used for strawberry cultivation under greenhouse conditions.

During the experiment, the properties of PE and PO film types were analysed, focusing on the effects of light on the vegetative and generative organs of the strawberry plants.

In greenhouse strawberry cultivation, pH and electrical conductivity (EC) levels are important factors for plant growth, development, and yield. The ideal pH level for strawberries is recommended to be between 5.5 and 6.5, as this range provides optimal conditions for nutrient absorption. EC, which depends on and thus represents the concentration of dissolved salts and nutrients in water, should typically be maintained between 0.8 and 1.5 mS/cm for strawberries. Keeping these parameters within the recommended ranges creates the ideal environment for strawberry growth and development. Conditions on the greenhouse with an automatically controlled environment during the research conducted between 2016 and 2019 were, for the case of the PE film cover on the substrate, pH level 5.5, relative air humidity at 72.5%, daytime temperature 22.5 °C, nighttime temperature 15.4 °C, and EC equal to 1.4 mS/cm under field conditions.

In the environment covered with PO film, the pH was 5.5, relative humidity was 72.8%, daytime temperature was 23.6 °C, night temperature was 17.3 °C, and EC was 1.5 mS/cm.

Regarding light transmittance, initial measurements in 2016 showed similar physical characteristics between both films. The PE film had a light transmittance of 85.8% and a light absorption rate of 7.4%. Comparatively, the PO film demonstrated slightly better performance with 2.1% higher light transmittance and 2.6% lower light absorption (Table 1). By the end of the experiment in 2019, significant changes were observed. In the greenhouse covered with PE film, light transmittance decreased by 19.4% to 66.4%, while light absorption increased by 1.1%. The PO film showed better durability, with light transmittance decreasing by only 8.4% to 79.5%, and light absorption increasing by 1.1% to 5.9%. Further analysis revealed that light reflectance in the PE film-covered greenhouse declined from 7.9% in 2016 to 4.9% in 2019.

Thus, light reflectance decrease for PE film is:

$$\text{Seasonal change} = \frac{7,9 - 4,9}{7,9} \times 100 \approx 37,97\% \text{ decrease.}$$

In the PO film, this indicator decreased by 7.7% in 2016 and by 6.8% at the end of the 2019 season, respectively. Light reflectance decrease for PO film is:

$$\text{Seasonal change} = \frac{7,7 - 6,8}{7,7} \times 100 \approx 11,69\% \text{ decrease.}$$

The results for light transmission were as follows:

In the greenhouse covered with PE film, it was 85.8% at the beginning of the 2016 season and 66.4% at the end of the 2019 season. Thus, decrease of light transmission for PE film is:

$$\text{Percent change} = \frac{85,8 - 66,4}{85,8} \times 100 \approx 22,63\% \text{ decrease.}$$

In a greenhouse where PO film is used, light transmission decreased as follows:

$$\text{Percent change} = \frac{87,9 - 79,5}{87,9} \times 100 \approx 9,56\% \text{ decrease.}$$

The results for increase in refractive index were as follows:

The refractive index in a greenhouse covered with PE film was 7.4% at the beginning of the 2016 season and increased to 14.4% by the end of the 2019 season, thus, increase is in the refractive index for PE film is:

$$\text{Percent change} = \frac{14,4 - 7,4}{7,4} \times 100 \approx 94,59\% \text{ increase.}$$

In the case of PO film, there was a 4.8% at the beginning of the season, and a 5.9% change at the end of the season, thus increase is:

$$\text{Percent change} = \frac{5,9 - 4,8}{4,8} \times 100 \approx 22,92\% \text{ increase.}$$

Table 1. Physical properties of films studied in the experimental field
(in 2016-2019, VTSYQI Haze Meter Touch Screen Hazemeter)

Film type	Thickness (mm)	Light Reflectance (%)	Light transmittance (%)	Refractive index (%)
At the beginning of the season, 2016				
PE	0,15	7,9	85,8	7,4
PO	0,15	7,7	87,9	4,8
At the end of the season, 2017				
PE	0,15	7,7	82,4	8,4
PO	0,15	7,7	86,3	4,9
At the beginning of the season, 2017				
PE	0,15	7,5	77,6	9,2
PO	0,15	7,6	84,2	5,1
At the end of the season, 2018				
PE	0,15	7,0	72,4	10,1
PO	0,15	7,4	81,3	5,3
At the beginning of the season, 2018				
PE	0,15	6,0	69,7	11,2
PO	0,15	7,1	80,2	5,7

At the end of the season, 2019				
PE	0,15	4,9	66,4	14,4
PO	0,15	6,8	79,5	5,9

By the end of the 2019 season, PE film showed light transmittance values of 58.7%, 54.7%, and 59.0% across different seasons, while PO film maintained higher values of 77.0%, 65.0%, and 78.0%, respectively. Research results confirmed that PO film demonstrated superior durability compared to PE film. Analysis of light transmittance patterns across seasons and daily hours revealed significant differences between the two materials. In fall 2016, PE film averaged 79.0% light transmittance, while PO film showed higher efficiency at 81.3%. As shown in Table 2, by 2019, PE film's performance had degraded substantially, dropping to 58.7% in autumn, while PO film maintained relatively high light transmittance at 77.0%. Examining the efficiency decline from 2016 to 2019, PE film showed decreased light transmittance across all seasons (autumn, winter, and spring), with autumn values dropping notably from 79.0% to 58.7%. While PO film also experienced some reduction in light transmission, the decrease was less pronounced compared to PE film.

Table 2. Light transmittance at intervals and daily hours, in %, LI-1400 Light Meter (LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA).

Seasonal breaks	Polyethylene (PE) film				Polyolefin (PO) film			
	Illuminance % per unit of time				Illuminance % per unit of time			
	8: 00	12: 00	16: 00	Average	8: 00	12: 00	16: 00	Average
At the beginning of the season, 2016								
Autumn	80,0	83,0	74,0	79,0	81,0	86,0	77,0	81,3
Winter	65,0	71,0	63,0	66,3	66,0	72,0	62,0	66,7
Spring	80,0	84,0	79,0	81,0	81,0	86,0	79,0	82,0
At the end of the season, 2019								
Autumn	57,0	67,0	52,0	58,7	76,0	81,0	74,0	77,0
Winter	52,0	63,0	49,0	54,7	64,0	70,0	61,0	65,0

Seasonal variations in light transmission were significant, with both films showing their lowest transmission indices during winter. By the end of 2019, PE film transmitted 54.7% of light, while PO film maintained a higher transmission rate of 65.0%. Spring measurements showed the highest light transmittance for both films compared to other seasons. Throughout all seasons, PO film consistently demonstrated superior light transmission and greater stability. The primary focus of our experimental field study was evaluating strawberry cultivation in greenhouses covered with PE and PO films. Analysis of light levels and their effects on strawberry photosynthetic activity led to several key findings.

3.2. Effects of Light Exposure on the Biological Parameters of Different Strawberry Cultivars.

Our research examined the biological properties of plant organs across different strawberry varieties under varying light conditions. The study analyzed growth indicators of Korean strawberry varieties ("Seolhyang", "Maehyang", "Jukhyang", "Keumsil", "King's Berry") and the

Japanese hybrid "Yotsuboshi F1" under PE and PO films. Key characteristics evaluated at 7 and 30 days after planting included crown diameter, plant height, main root length, and plant wet and dry weights. Initial data collected on October 7, 2016, showed no significant variations among the newly planted seedlings across all varieties and hybrids, confirming successful establishment of the transplants. As shown in Table 3, on October 7, "Seolhyang" plants under both PE and PO films either lacked crown formation or had their crowns removed. Measurements showed plant heights of 6.8-6.5 cm, main root lengths of 8.4-8.2 mm, wet weights of 15.7-15.5 g, and dry weights of 1.56-1.50 g. The "King's Berry" variety demonstrated superior performance, exceeding all measured parameters compared to "Maehyang", "Jukhyang", "Keumsil", and "Yotsuboshi F1".

Table 3. Growth parameters of different strawberry cultivars under light exposure (Measurements taken 7 and 30 days after planting, October 1-30, 2016).

№	Strawberry varieties	Features of the plant				
		Crown diameter (mm)	Plant height (cm)	Root length (cm)	Wet weight (g)	Dry weight (g)
7 days after planting seedlings						
1.	"Seolhyang"		6,8	8,4	15,7	1,56
2.	"Maehyang"		6,6	8,2	15,4	1,52
3.	"Jukhyang"		6,9	8,0	15,0	1,49
4.	"Keumsil"		6,7	7,9	14,9	1,38
5.	"King's Berry"		7,1	8,9	16,0	1,57
6.	"Yotsuboshi F1"		6,4	7,9	15,5	1,51
7.	"Seolhyang"		6,5	8,2	15,5	1,50
8.	"Maehyang"		6,4	8,0	15,3	1,48
9.	"Jukhyang"		6,8	8,2	15,2	1,47
10.	"Keumsil"		6,5	8,0	15,0	1,49
11.	"King's Berry"		7,2	9,1	16,2	1,59
12.	"Yotsuboshi F1"		6,5	7,9	15,6	1,50
30 days after planting seedlings						
1.	"Seolhyang"	3,2	8,7	17,3	27,8	2,94
2.	"Maehyang"	3,5	8,8	16,8	25,8	2,56
3.	"Jukhyang"	3,0	8,2	17,0	28,2	2,91
4.	"Keumsil"	2,8	8,5	15,8	26,8	2,73
5.	"King's Berry"	4,3	9,3	16,6	26,9	2,85
6.	"Yotsuboshi F1"	3,2	9,2	13,9	23,5	2,54
7.	"Seolhyang"	3,4	8,8	16,7	26,8	2,78
8.	"Maehyang"	3,5	8,9	14,9	26,2	2,55
9.	"Jukhyang"	3,0	8,3	16,4	27,2	3,01
10.	"Keumsil"	2,9	8,7	14,6	27,0	2,65

11.	"King's Berry"	4,4	9,5	15,9	26,2	2,67
12.	"Yotsuboshi F1"	3,5	9,0	13,3	22,9	2,48

After 30 days, "Seolhyang" (Korea's standard commercial variety) grown under PE and PO films showed the following development: crown diameter (3.2-3.7 mm), plant height (8.7-8.8 cm), main root length (17.3-16.7 cm), wet weight (27.8-26.8 g), and dry weight (2.94-2.78 g).

These measurements indicated that "Seolhyang" possessed higher biological potential during initial growth stages compared to "Keumsil", "Jukhyang", and "Yotsuboshi F1". "King's Berry" variety demonstrated superior growth in some parameters compared to "Seolhyang", with crown diameter measuring 1.1-1.2 mm larger and plant height 0.6-0.7 cm taller.

However, it showed slightly lower measurements in other aspects: main root length was 0.7-0.8 cm shorter, plant wet weight was 0.9-0.6 g less, and dry weight was 0.09-0.11 g lower. The expression of biological characteristics in strawberry varieties is genetically inherited from parent plants through specific genes. Transplantation stress directly affects plant metabolism, influencing their physiological characteristics.

Plant development phases are governed by genetic characteristics unique to each variety. This process is regulated by specific genes controlling physiological and biochemical changes, particularly auxin and ethylene balance reactions. When these genes experience stress, growth and development processes are affected for varying periods, resulting in distinctive changes.

The organ formation in each variety and hybrid genetically may be influenced through the following key factors: 1) Light Management through PE and PO Films. These films regulate spectral light content, directly impacting plant photosynthesis through controlled illumination and spectral transmittance. "Seolhyang" and "King's Berry" varieties demonstrate particular sensitivity to red and blue light spectral wavelengths, thus enabling optimal photosynthesis and resulting in accelerated growth compared to other varieties. 2) Temperature Regulation. Greenhouse films maintain optimal temperature conditions by preserving daytime heat and preventing sharp nighttime temperature drops. This temperature stability enhances plant physiological resilience, accelerating enzymatic processes and cell division. 3) Humidity Control. PE and PO films effectively manage both soil moisture and air humidity levels. Under these optimal moisture conditions, "Seolhyang" and "King's Berry" varieties develop more robust root systems, leading to enhanced water and nutrient absorption.

The physiological characteristics of these varieties facilitate active transport of growth hormones (auxin, cytokinin, and gibberellin), promoting cell elongation and division. The controlled microclimate created by the films supports these processes, fostering optimal plant development.

3.3. Physiological leaf changes in different strawberry varieties under light exposure.

Research conducted during 2016-2017 revealed significant physiological changes in strawberry leaves by day 30 in greenhouses covered with PE and PO films. The study focused on two key measurements: SPAD index and leaf area. These parameters provide crucial insights for plant physiology and agronomic research through three main aspects: 1) Photosynthetic Efficiency Assessment. The SPAD indicator measures leaf chlorophyll content, the primary pigment in photosynthesis crucial for light absorption and plant nutrition. This measurement serves as a dual indicator, evaluating both photosynthetic efficiency and plant nitrogen status, given the scientifically established presence of nitrogen in chlorophyll molecules. 2) Growth and Development Evaluation. Leaf area serves as a key indicator of plant growth capacity. Larger leaf

areas typically correlate with higher photosynthetic efficiency and increased productivity. This measurement also helps assess plant adaptation to various environmental conditions and their response to stress factors, including water deficiency, nutrient limitations, and temperature fluctuations. 3) Yield Prediction. The combination of SPAD readings and leaf area measurements enables prediction of strawberry plant yield potential. These parameters inform optimal agronomic practices and provide valuable yield forecasting capabilities for both research and practical applications.

In 2016-2017, "Seolhyang" variety grown in both PE and PO greenhouses showed SPAD index values of 47.02-47.30 and leaf area measurements of 189.6-197.7 cm²/plant (Table 4. Comparative analysis of SPAD indicators revealed distinct patterns:

- "Maehyang", "Jukhyang", and "Keumsil" varieties demonstrated higher SPAD values by 1.21-1.99, 1.39-1.15, and 1.05-1.08 units respectively.
- "King's Berry" and "Yotsuboshi F1" showed lower values by 1.41-1.94 and 0.3-1.1 units respectively.

Leaf area measurements using the LI-3000C Portable Area Meter showed that "Seolhyang" had smaller leaf surface area compared to "Jukhyang" and "Yotsuboshi F1" hybrid (30.1-37.2 and 6.6-0.8 cm²/plant less, respectively). However, "Seolhyang" demonstrated larger leaf areas compared to: "Maehyang" (18.1-13.1 cm²/plant); "Keumsil" (14.5-9.9 cm²/plant); and "King's Berry" (14.5-42.1 cm²/plant).

Table 4. Changes in leaf physiology in strawberry cultivars under the influence of light, results obtained in 2016-2017 (Chlorophyll measurement - (SPAD-502) instrument, leaf level, LI-3000C Portable Area Meter instrument).

№	Strawberry varieties	Polyethylene (PE) film		Polyolefin (PO) film	
		SPAD indicator	Leaf area (cm ² / plant)	SPAD indicator	Leaf area (cm ² / plant)
7 days after planting					
1.	"Seolhyang"	37,77	134,3	38,35	135,2
2.	"Maehyang"	39,63	132,9	40,12	148,9
3.	"Jukhyang"	38,47	116,7	39,30	113,8
4.	"Keumsil"	38,41	126,5	39,21	143,8
5.	"King's Berry"	36,28	152,7	36,93	160,8
6.	"Yotsuboshi F1"	37,23	106,8	37,43	107,9
30 days after planting					
7.	"Seolhyang"	47,02	189,6	47,30	197,7
8.	"Maehyang"	48,23	207,7	49,29	210,8
9.	"Jukhyang"	48,41	159,5	48,45	160,5
10.	"Keumsil"	48,07	204,1	48,38	207,6
11.	"King's Berry"	45,61	235,9	45,36	239,8
12.	"Yotsuboshi F1"	46,72	183,0	46,20	196,9

Studies conducted during 2017-2019 showed that varying light levels affected morphological and physiological characteristics in genetically diverse varieties and hybrids. SPAD index and leaf area parameters remained consistent with previous years' observations. However, the degradation of films over time led to decreased light transmission, resulting in slower

photosynthetic processes and reduced chlorophyll pigment formation in leaves. In conclusion, "Seolhyang" maintained moderate SPAD index values in both PE and PO film-covered greenhouses, while some varieties like "Maehyang" and "Jukhyang" showed higher chlorophyll content. Despite having a smaller leaf area compared to certain varieties, "Seolhyang" demonstrated stable physiological development.

3.4. Impact of greenhouse film types on strawberry variety productivity.

Research results from 2016-2019 revealed clear correlations between strawberry plant productivity and lighting conditions. Analysis of average productivity during this period demonstrated significant variations based on film type.

Film Type Effects on Light Transmission and Yield:

PE Film Performance:

- Light transmission decreased significantly from 79% (2016) to 59% (2019) as shown in Table 2.
- Reduced light levels led to decreased photosynthetic activity and lower productivity.
- "Seolhyang" variety yields declined from 34.4 t/ha (2016-2017) to 22.7 t/ha (2018-2019).

PO Film Advantages:

- Maintained superior light transmission (78% through spring 2019).
- Demonstrated consistently higher productivity compared to PE film.
- "Seolhyang" averaged 34.3 t/ha under PO film, exceeding PE film yields by 5.0 t/ha.

Long-term Yield Stability:

The superior performance of PO film was particularly evident in yield stability across varieties. For instance, "King's Berry" variety in 2018-2019 produced 24.8 t/ha under PE film, and 34.6 t/ha under PO film, representing a 4.5 t/ha yield advantage. This enhanced productivity under PO film can be attributed to its sustained light transmission efficiency, creating optimal conditions for photosynthesis throughout the growing season (Table 4).

Table 4. Plant productivity of strawberry varieties under the influence of light (average indicators in 2016-2019).

№	Strawberry varieties	Productivity, t/ha			The average yield is t/ha	Additional yield compared to PE, t/ha
		2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019		
Polyethylene film (PE)						
1.	"Seolhyang"	34,4±0,70	30,9±0,40	22,7±0,10	29,3	-
2.	"Maehyang"	33,5±0,70	28,7±0,62	21,9±0,36	28,0	-
3.	"Jukhyang"	31,8±0,36	26,8±0,36	18,8±0,49	25,8	-
4.	"Keumsil"	32,8±0,30	28,0±0,30	20,2±0,20	27,0	-
5.	"King's Berry"	37,7±0,44	33,6±0,10	24,8±0,26	32,0	-
6.	"Yotsuboshi F1"	35,5±0,30	31,7±0,36	24,8±0,20	30,7	-
Polyolefin (PO) film						
7.	"Seolhyang"	36,5±0,44	34,2±0,17	32,1±0,26	34,3	+5,0
8.	"Maehyang"	34,7±0,70	31,8±0,26	28,3±0,26	31,6	+3,6
9.	"Jukhyang"	32,1±0,36	29,9±0,35	26,4±0,36	29,5	+3,7
10.	"Keumsil"	33,0±0,46	30,7±0,20	27,2±0,26	30,3	+3,3

11.	"King's Berry"	38,2±0,26	36,7±0,36	34,6±0,20	36,5	+4,5
12.	"Yotsuboshi F1"	36,3±0,26	34,2±0,26	33,4±0,20	34,6	+3,9

Light Levels and Plant Performance:

Light intensity directly influences plant photosynthesis. Reduced light levels lead to decreased chlorophyll synthesis, resulting in slower photosynthetic rates. This cascade effect reduces organic matter production and ultimately decreases yield.

Film Performance Comparison: PO film's superior light transmission maintained high photosynthetic intensity, resulting in better yields. Throughout 2016-2019, yield patterns showed marked differences between film types:

PE Film:

- Sharp yield decline observed.
- "Seolhyang" yields dropped from 34.4 t/ha to 22.7 t/ha.

PO Film:

- Maintained stable yields between 36.5 t/ha to 32.1 t/ha.
- Consistently provided 3.3-5.0 t/ha additional yield compared to PE film.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Film properties change over time, affecting their light transmission capabilities. Research findings demonstrated that PE film experienced significant degradation, with average light transmission decreasing by 20% between 2016 and 2019. This decline was particularly pronounced during the winter months, when transmission rates dropped from 66.3% to 54.7%. In contrast, PO film exhibited remarkable stability, as its light transmission decreased by only 4.0-5.0% throughout the study period, showcasing superior durability compared to PE film. Seasonal observations revealed that both film types achieved peak light transmission during spring and autumn, coinciding with increased natural light availability in the external environment.

The results of this study indicate a direct correlation between light availability and strawberry productivity and fruit quality. Reduced light conditions consistently led to decreased productivity, lower SPAD index values, and a smaller leaf area. These negative effects were particularly evident in plants grown under PE film, where declining light transmission negatively impacted plant performance. From 2016 to 2019, yields under PE film decreased to 5.0 t/ha due to reduced light levels. In contrast, PO film maintained stable light conditions, allowing for an additional average yield of 3.3-5.0 t/ha.

The reduction of light under PE film slowed photosynthesis, ultimately hindering plant growth and productivity. Therefore, PO film is preferred for optimal long-term light retention and productivity. PO film's superior light retention properties translated into tangible productivity benefits, consistently yielding an additional 3.3-5.0 t/ha compared to PE film. This enhanced yield can be attributed to the film's ability to maintain optimal light conditions, supporting sustained photosynthetic activity throughout the growing season. These results clearly demonstrate the advantages of using PO film for long-term greenhouse cultivation, particularly in maintaining stable growing conditions and supporting consistent plant productivity.

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